

Significance of Trikonasana in Healthy Life

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is the science of life. It plays an important role to prevent and treat the disease. Ayurveda specifically deals with mind body balance. The main part of it is Yoga and Asana. Yoga provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health. Asana gives physical and mental power and tone the body-mind for further exercise. Trikonasana is often referred to as the Triangle Pose. This pose helps improve flexibility in the spine and can also be used to correct shoulder alignment. Also benefits the lower body and strengthens knees and ankles. Trikonasana (Triangle Pose) compresses the side abdominal muscles (the side that is towards the floor), while also stretching the opposite side of the abdominal muscles deeper.

KEYWORDS: Yoga, Asana, Trikonasana, Triangle Pose, abdominal muscles

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda play an important role to prevent and treat the disease. It is the science of life. Health is disturbed today by the sedentary lifestyle, physical and mental pressure or stress, abnormal personal habits and food habits which cause many disease. According to various texts the primary goal of Ayurveda is – “Swasthasya Swastya Rakshanam, Aturasya Vikara Prashamanam”^[1] which means increasing the good health and treat the disease. Ayurveda specifically deals with mind body balance. The main part of it is Yoga and Asana.. It is essential to being healthy. Yoga appeared at the time of the Vedas and Upanishads. Yoga is India's oldest scientific, ideal devotional regulation. It is a process of teaching the brain and growing its capacity of fine perceptions. Yoga provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health and hygiene to gain physical and mental fitness in less time.^[2] Yoga is praised by modern medical science because it increase immunity, give disease free life and decrease the stress of present fast life. It is a scientific procedure by which we can develop our own inner strength with inself. In Sanskrit language Yoga means “adduction”, add the soul of human from the God. Yoga provides us moral and spiritual growth but also useful in prevent physical and mental disease.^[3] Yoga and Asana effect the physiology of important anatomical structure during procedure and steps.^[4] The definition of Asana is “Sthira Sukham Asanas”^[5] which means well balanced, pleasant

position of body. Asana are the “skillful exercises” that gives physical and mental power and tone the body-mind for further exercise.^[6] Asana helps to synchronize the mind with body.^[7]

Yogasana

Patanjali Yoga described about eight branches –Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dharna, Dhyan, Samadhi. Patanjali Yoga given third place to Asana^[8], while “Hatha Yoga” given first place to “Asana” because it giving physical and mental happiness. “Ha” means sun which means energy of solar plexus, “Tha” means moon which means energy of the emotions, present in the limbic system of brain, so both the energy come together in the Yoga.^[9] If Asanas is done accurately in relaxed and pleasant atmosphere, the muscles of the body get relax because these relaxing impulses go back to the brain and relax it. Other benefits are mental balance, good health, calmness of mind. The ancient Yogacharyas advised about the mastery of one Asana. Trikonasana (Triangle Pose) helps improve flexibility in the spine and can also be used to correct shoulder alignment. Also benefits the lower body and strengthens knees and ankles. This pose compresses the side abdominal muscles (the side that is towards the floor), while also stretching the opposite side of the abdominal muscles deeper.^[10]

Aim and Objectives

- To elaborate the benefits and anatomical structures of *Trikonasana*.
- To escape from injuries which held by doing *Trikonasana*.

Material and Methods

- Texts related to *Yoga-Asana* and their commentaries.
- Other source are online information, print media, journals etc.
- Triangle Pose is considered a base pose as triangle pose variations can be derived from this pose.

Trikonasana

In Sanskrit, 'tri' = 'three', 'kona' = 'angle, corners', 'asana' = 'posture'. Hence *Trikonasana* just means 'three corners' and the English title is Triangle Pose. This is a standing basic beginner level yoga pose and forms part of almost all styles of yoga. A great way to open the hips, while also stretching the muscles around the spine. Compared to the practice of *Utthita Trikonasana* (Extended Triangle Pose), this requires more flexibility of the hips and the side abdominal muscles.^[11]

Common name	Triangle Pose
English name	Triangle Pose
Sanskrit name	<i>Trikonasana</i>
All	Triangle Pose, <i>Trikonasana</i>
Level	Intermediate
Position	Standing
Type	Side-Bend, Stretch
Chakras	Heart Chakra (<i>Anahata Chakra</i>) , Sacral Chakra (<i>Swadisthana Chakra</i>) , Root Chakra (<i>Muladhara Chakra</i>)
Dosha	<i>Vata</i> , <i>Pitta</i> , <i>Kapha</i>
Elements	Air , Water , Earth

Steps

- Stand erect. Now, keep distance between your legs about 3 to 4 feet
- Extend your arms at the shoulder level.
- Inhale and raises your right arm by the side of your head.
- Now, bend your right arms with exhaling towards the left side by keeping your body weight equally on both the feet. You should ensure that the right arm become parallel to the ground.
- Maintain the position as per your comfort with normal breathing and come to the original position by inhaling.
- Do the same procedure with the left arm.
- Perform three to five rounds of *Trikonasana*.^[12]

Fig. Performing Trikonasana

Triangle Pose Benefits

With the practice of *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose), the benefits derived would be the same as with the practice of *Utthita Trikonasana* (Extended Triangle Pose). But as the position of the hand is different in both, the additional benefits derived are mentioned below:

1. **Hips:** In this variation of Triangle Pose, the hand when placed behind stretches one side the hip joint while the other side flexes with compression of the hip joint and the various muscles around it. This increases the flexibility of the hip to a great extent.
2. **Shoulders:** When the arms extend to reach behind the foot, the shoulders stretch more, improving the flexibility too.

3. **Alignment:** Only with proper alignment can the hand be placed behind the foot and hence the focus towards the same will help with challenging yoga poses too.
4. **Advance yoga pose:** The practice of *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose) helps to prepare for Fallen Star Pose (*Patita Tarasana*), which is a deeper variation of Triangle Pose.
5. **Abdominal muscles:** *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose) compresses the side abdominal muscles (the side that is towards the floor), while also stretching the opposite side of the abdominal muscles deeper.^[13]

Triangle Pose Contraindications

Trikonasana (Triangle Pose) is a lateral bending posture and with this come a few contraindications or precautions to keep in mind. Given below are these precautions explained:

1. **Injury:** Students with an injury of the back like; slip disc or disc bulge should avoid the practice of *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose). Those with issues related to the knee, hips, ankles, shoulders, neck, or the abdominal area should take proper guidance from a yoga teacher to avoid further complications.
2. **Women:** While women during their first trimester can practice this under the guidance of a yoga teacher, but during the second trimester and third trimester should use block for better support if very comfortable with breathing, and otherwise have no other health issues.
3. **Blood Pressure and Heart:** Breathing can get difficult while doing a lateral bend especially for those students suffering from blood pressure or having heart related issues. Hence best done in a modified way and then go slowly into the complete Triangle Pose. The option of this modification can be this at *Utthita Trikonasana* Block (Extended Triangle Pose Block), or *Trikonasana* Chair (Triangle Pose Chair).
4. Read up on the contraindications of *Utthita Trikonasana* (Extended Triangle Pose) also before practicing Triangle Pose.^[14]

Precautions

Though the pose is beneficial to your body in many ways, it should not be performed if you are suffering from diarrhea, low blood pressure, headaches, and migraines or have back injuries. If you have any heart condition or high blood pressure, do not turn your head or your torso with jerky movements. Also, practice the pose when resting against a wall. Do not overextend your upper arm. Additionally, those with spinal injuries or neck problems should avoid the pose completely.

Beginner's Tip

The pose requires a considerable amount of balance, so if you are not feeling up to it, consider using the support of a wall while performing the pose. This is the best beginner's tip for the triangle pose as it, keeps you anchored and also keeps you from toppling over. You can also use wooden yoga blocks to support your stride. These props let you stretch your stride as much as you can manage. Simply place the yoga blocks right next to your feet when you are expanding your stride. This will help you maintain your balance, especially when you are a yoga beginner. As you get better, you may no longer need the blocks.

Benefit to a specific Body Part

- The thighs receive the most benefit when one performs this yoga pose regularly. This pose helps make your thighs flexible and tones up those thigh muscles.
- This pose helps improve flexibility in the spine and can also be used to correct shoulder alignment.
- Also benefits the lower body and strengthens knees and ankles.
- Tones the muscles in the arms and strengthens the neck.^[15]

Anatomy

Triangle Pose benefits the following muscles and hence can be included in yoga sequences with the corresponding muscles:-

- Arms and Shoulders
- Lower Back
- Biceps and Triceps
- Core (Abs)
- Hamstrings
- Chest
- Psoas
- Quadriceps^[16]

Fig. Anatomy of effected structures by *Trikonasana*

Therapeutic Applications

There are several therapeutic applications to this pose.

- While the pose does offer flexibility and improved balance to the body, it is considered an excellent pose for dealing with stress. The balance that you achieve with this pose can also help you bring mental peace.
- Can be used to manage stomach irritants such as flatulence, gastritis, acidity, indigestion, and

- constipation. It massages the abdominal organs and gives them a thorough work out.
- This pose also provides a massage to the pelvic organs and can be helpful in problems related to the reproductive system.
- The *Trikonasana* is helpful in the treatment of backaches and neck sprains and other joint and muscle related problems.
- It also helps in Improving circulation.

Variations

One of the variations of the triangle pose is known as extended triangle pose. In this pose, instead of stretching your top arm towards the ceiling, you can also stretch it over the back of your ear, keeping your arm parallel to the floor. This is an easy variation that can help you master the pose and also pose a greater challenge for balancing. You can also try aligning the front heel with the back foot arch to add to the difficulty level of the pose.

Other variations include:

- *Baddha Trikonasana* (**Bound Triangle Pose**)
- *Parivritta Trikonasana* (**Revolved Triangle Pose**)
- *Baddha Parivritta Trikonasana* (**Bound Revolved Triangle Pose**)
- *Supta Trikonasana* (**Reclining Triangle Pose**).^[17]
- *Trikonasana* Prep Arms Up
- Fallen Triangle Pose *Patita Tarasana*
- *Trikonasana* Variation Hand On Shin^[18]

Triangle Pose yoga sequences

Triangle Pose is commonly found in the following types of yoga sequences:

- Kids yoga sequences
- Teens Yoga sequences
- Core yoga sequences
- Heart opening yoga sequences
- Power Yoga Sequence King Pigeon Pose
- Ashtanga Yoga Primary Series
- Yoga For Women Yoga Sequence For Menstruation

Triangle Pose Breath Awareness

Given below are the breathing instructions for the practice of *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose):

- From *Utthita Tadasana*, inhale and bring the feet to 90 degrees and 45 degrees respectively.
- Exhale, adjust the feet and the hips.
- Inhale, bend the torso towards the side, reaching for the floor with your hand.
- Exhale, place the palm on the floor. Inhale raise the other arm up and gaze at the extended arm.
- Inhale and Exhale to stay in *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose).
- Exhale, to stretch further into the posture.
- Inhale, release the hand and come up with the torso.
- Exhale, relax in *Utthita Trikonasana*.
- Follow the same instructions while practicing with the other side.^[19]

Preparatory Poses

Since the practice of *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose) involves balance, strong and flexible hamstrings and quadriceps, flexible hips, open shoulders and chest, the need to prepare before moving into this pose is important. Given below are some of the preparatory poses that can help with the above mentioned areas of the body to open:

- *Utthita Ashwa Sanchalanasana* (Runners Lunge Pose).
- *Virabhadrasana II* (Warrior Pose II).
- *Prasarita Padottanasana* (Intense Leg Stretch Pose).
- *Utthita Parsvakonasana* (Extended Side Angle Pose, Variation Elbow Arm).^[20]
- *Tadasana* (Mountain Pose)
- *Adho Mukha Savasana* (Downward Facing Dog Pose)
- *Vrikshasana* (Tree Pose)^[21]

Follow-up Poses

Post the practice of Triangle Pose (*Trikonasana*) which is a lateral bend with feet apart, there are some ways to rest the hamstrings and the hips acting as counter poses:

- *Uttanasana* (Standing Forward Bend Pose).
- *Tadasana* (Mountain Pose).
- *Dandasana* (Staff Pose).^[22]

Conclusion

Yoga is the science of life. *Yoga* is India's oldest scientific, ideal devotional regulation. It is a process of teaching the brain and growing its capacity of fine perceptions. *Yoga* provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health and hygiene to gain physical and mental fitness in less time. Daily practice of *Yoga*, *Asana* and *Pranayama* with proper attention gives result pure blood supply to body parts like heart, liver, lungs, pancreas, intestine, kidney, ligaments, tissues, muscles, and glands of human body. It also increases the digestion power. It control power of the sense organs and awareness. *Yoga* and *Asana* will give disease and stress free healthy life. Anatomical structures during breath and postures as lungs, ligaments, muscles and bones, ligaments, joints, muscles and tendon during movement are involved. Anatomical structures and their work are behind the scientific benefit of *Yoga* and *Asana*. Triangle pose helps improve flexibility in the spine and can also be used to correct shoulder alignment. Also benefits the lower body and strengthens knees and ankles. *Trikonasana* (Triangle Pose) compresses the side abdominal muscles (the side that is towards the floor), while also stretching the opposite side of the abdominal muscles deeper.

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